

From Silent Suffering to Emancipation and Empowerment of Dalit Women: 'A Study of Dalit Women Autobiographies'

Bojja Pranathi Shubhasri

Research Scholar, Department of English
Osmania University

Abstract

The journey of Dalit women in India from silent suffering to emancipation and empowerment is a poignant and powerful narrative. Historically marginalized and oppressed, Dalit women have faced a unique intersection of caste and gender discrimination. Through their autobiographies, these women have found a voice to articulate their struggles, resilience, and triumphs. This study explores the autobiographies of Dalit women, shedding light on their lived experiences and the systemic injustices they have endured. By examining their personal narratives, the research aims to highlight the transformative journey of Dalit women from subjugation to self-assertion. These autobiographies not only document their hardships but also celebrate their indomitable spirit and quest for dignity and equality. The study delves into the themes of identity, resistance, and empowerment, offering a comprehensive understanding of the Dalit women's movement in India.

Keywords: Dalit women, autobiography, quest for dignity and equality, identity, women's movement etc.

Emancipation of Dalit woman is also the emancipation of Indian women which became utmost important when India was struggling for political emancipation from the British rule. Today we are talking about emancipation and empowerment of women. But in the past there was a time when women had no voice in self and society. The social reformers created awareness in the society in particular women where the practices, customs and moral conduct and rules of life were designed by the 'hydra headed' patriarchal society. Women were inspired to break the chains of traditional life patterns to participate in the new possibilities and opportunities in the nineteenth century for the emancipation of women from all social slavery to come into terms of equality of gender.

One of the pioneers of Social Reformers like Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Jotirao Phule fought against the inhuman treatment by orthodox Brahmins towards shudras and women. This step marks the historical beginning in the social discourse of equality for all through education.

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Jotirao Phule challenged the very code of Hindu Scriptures and spread the essence of education to all by opening schools. Dr. Baba Saheb Ambedkar, a great social reformer aimed primarily at social freedom, social injustice, social evils and women's degradation. His thought and vision were greatly influenced by his social background and his own bitter experiences as one from a depressed class.

Manusmriti laid down certain rules and a code of conduct for women where women were denied freedom in any respect. Hence Ambedkar introduced Hindu code Bill in the constituent Assembly. Thus it recognised the status of woman as equal to that of man. Ambedkar wanted to re-organise and reconstruct the Hindu society from the grassroots level. To reform Hinduism, Dr. Ambedkar burnt Manusmriti in public which was a milestone in the struggle against Brahminism. Henceforth he devoted his life to eradicate untouchability and purify the Hindu society.

Gendering of the Autobiography

The genre of autobiography in literature has focussed only on masculine and middle-class. Autobiographies narrate a truth that is shared and endorsed by everyone. In the process, it could be seen that in this field, women's autobiographies have drawn attention to the absence of women's texts. These autobiographies have been defined by feminist critics as texts with reference to life and its philosophy. It is to be understood that "*difference*" becomes an important term to show the concept of gendered narrative with reference to women's autobiographies and their status herewith. Difference has been restrained not just to sexual difference but has been "*pluralisation of difference*", across race, gender, ethnicity, class and sexuality. (Anderson,117). Therefore, autobiographies are self-narratives where there is an intersection of autobiography as well as history.

Dalit autobiographies were a part of Dalit literature which arrived onto the scene of Indian literature causing much anxiety among the gatekeepers of literary establishments. During the 1990s, various Dalit women's autobiographies began coming out in vernacular languages such as Marathi, Tamil and Hindi etc. Fortunately, these women writers turned out to be the few Dalits who managed to move out of their villages to educate themselves. Their autobiographies not only presented the life of an individual but also the past and the present of

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their own communities, their live experiences, both individual and collective. Therefore, we can say that the emphasis is on experiential emotion, rather than on language.

The autobiography of 'Baisantri' is around the community she was living in. She gives various references of her everyday activities and the problems she faced both within and outside the community. Caste bias is attacked; the prime focus of the autobiography is not this though. She speaks of her family and other people living around her giving us a clear picture of a Dalit community. The focus is on the facts of how they live what their culture is. Her usage of "we" instead of "I" in her autobiography reveals the way the individual here is speaking for the community and this paves the way for the portrayal of collective consciousness. Dalit autobiographies are mostly based on rural India where the authors have spent the early part of their lives. There is a subsequent shift to the urban parts where one can see less discrimination comparatively.

The mainstream Indian feminism describes Dalit feminism as a "discourse of discontent" and "a politics of difference". The question is not only claiming of Indian feminism's hegemony to speak for all women, but also of Dalit men to speak on behalf of Dalit women. Evidently, Dalit feminists visualised three- way oppression of Dalit women subject to caste oppression in the hands of upper castes, to class-biased oppression in the hands of hundreds of landowners and finally of those who experience patriarchal oppression in the hands of all men, including men of their own caste, says 'Uma Chakravarti'. 'Bama', 'Baby Kamble', 'Urmila Pavar' and many more Dalit women writers have been penning to bring forward their experiences of humiliation for centuries. One of the most acclaimed and a distinguished Dalit women writer in Tamil is Bama Faustina, who gained fame for her autobiographical novel, *Karukku* in the year 1992. It turned out to be the first Tamil Dalit text on the Christian Dalit community. Her original name is Faustina Mary Fatima Rani. Faustina is a Latin name. She said once,

"Mary is overtly Christian, Fatima could also be a Muslim name and Rani means" queen" which does not appeal to me. I wanted a different sort of name so I took the first and the last syllables of Fatima and made of this name Bama".(Online source)

'Sangati' is one of Bama's significant episodic novels and is a record of Dalit women experiences portraying their oppression of caste and gender faced by them. In other terms, it is a portrayal of a community's autobiography. The novel analyses dual patriarchies, one of their own caste and the other of the upper caste and poverty as well. The novel shows an account of their suffering in the community and in the institutions in caste courts, the Church and in the Panchayats in terms of labour, domestic violence including their own ignorance and finally suggests remedies. (Ramakrishnan, 2011: 67)

The novel seeks to show the exploitation, threat of molest by the upper caste thus locating male violence even in their caste. Bama shows a strong difference of Dalit women from the privileged upper caste women celebrating their identity in their strength, power, labour and resilience.

The first of its kind in Tamil, *Karukku* was not only the first Dalit autobiography but achieved a specific identity, having written by a Dalit Christian Woman. Dalit movements dominated mostly by men had a tendency to sideline issues concerning Dalit women. The Dalit women were compelled to voice their misery doubled up due to caste and gender discrimination. The result was the rise of Dalit Feminism. As an exponent of Dalit Feminism, Bama has found in *Karukku* the right space to articulate the travails and sufferings of Dalit women. *Karukku* thus enjoys the unique recognition of being one of the first radical feminist discourses by a Tamil Dalit woman. Though written in Tamil in 1992, *Karukku* won worldwide acclaim only after Lakshmi Holmstrom translated it to English in 2000. The English translation has enabled *Karukku* to cross linguistic and regional boundaries, and reach the global readers. Many Dalit writers commented *Karukku* is a reflection of different themes like religion, recreation, and education, etc. Through these perspectives, Bama gives us a clear picture of the caste oppression meted out to the Dalit Christians not only by the upper caste society but more so within the catholic church itself. Caste as a political identity enables the subordinated caste identity to "affirm the solidarity of a community, regain the world and affirm self-possession and confidence" (13) and change existing equations of power.

Bama as a feminist writer raised articulation against all forms of oppression on Dalit women and appealed for all the Dalit women to change and win self empowerment through education and collective action. Simultaneously written novel by Bama is *Vanmam – Vendetta* in the year 2008 that pins out the internal differences among Dalits. This novel also attacks on

the oppression on Dalit women. To Bama, Dalit Literature is a critique of the Hindu social order but not merely Literature on Dalits.

“It is a hidden histories of hurt and humiliation and is a picture of a site where the inequalities of caste system are shown in terms of purity and pollution”. (Rao, 2003:3). It is important to note that women are subjugated in sphere of life both by men of upper caste and by her own caste irrespective of these happenings between Dalits and Elite sections or Dalits with sub sections. The novel *Vanmam Vendetta* is about animosity between two castes within Dalits, Pallars and Parayars. Pallars identified themselves as Hindus and Parayars are mostly Christian converts. Gail Omvedt, a renowned Dalit scholar says of *Vanmam* :

"In almost every region of India there are two main (Dalit) castes, often at odds." (Indian Express, New Delhi, August 9, 2008).

Through the novella, Bama has laid a strong dichotomous structure that is not only simple but detrimental to Dalit's oppressed life.

According to Bama, Dalit literature is not merely a collection of texts, but is that that marks the emergence of a new self consciousness. This is the philosophy marked by Dr. Ambedkar and the writers of this movement that shows clearly “an awareness of belonging to a distinct literary culture and society”. (Devy, 2006: 126).

The novel presents how the land owners of the dominating Naicker caste ignited the fire between Pallars and Parayas in order to preserve their own status. *Vanmam* documents the hatred and vengeance among the various Dalit communities, an area too touchy to be addressed and too complex to be grasped. It is sad but true that the graded inequality that sustains caste order is replicated among the Dalits as well. The hierarchy among Dalits in Tamil Nadu has the following structure as a given: Pallar, Parayar and Arundathiyar. The novel has chosen to deal with the top two castes among the Dalits and not the hierarchically positioned Arundathiyar, for example. The idyllic bonding between the two communities built through cultural events, sports and celebration of festivals turns out to be a mere façade to mask the burning jealousies over socio-economic issues. Unfortunately, conversion to Christianity becomes the key variable in causing this divide.

The bloody caste clashes begin with a Hindu Pallar murdering a Christian Parayar. The story ends with the murder of an innocent Parayar that leads to the dawn of realisation among both the parties about how they have been made pawns in the hands of caste Hindus. Finally a resolution sought in electoral politics (a document from the Hindu, Nov 2, 2008).

In the interview appended to the novel, Bama says that the events she narrated in Vanmam are limited to a particular village. So, one cannot take it as a generalised statement. But it is difficult not to get into generalised conclusions. More so in translated texts. What one would sense while reading a text in Tamil with all its regional and caste variations of diction, usage and relationship among the speakers get lost in English.

There is a graphic description of the village Kandampatli in rural Tamilnadu. The novel is set in the clavadey, the market place, the fields and orchards, and the streets of the Pallars, Parayars and Naikers. The description is more than just the topography of the village. We draw the outline of the village where various castes function and interact depending upon the dynamics of the multi caste village. Azagarasan says, “the calm is a strategy and background to the storm clouds that soon arrive”. The enmity between the Parayars and Pallars begin leading to jealousies and running feuds, resulting in the murder of a Parayar by a Pallar. There are a series of retaliations and counter retaliations found ending in a caste clash axiomatically.

To quote the text,

“The heroes of the story appear to be the young, educated Parayar youth. They are depicted in all their mischievousness and haughtiness: Jayaraju, who begins as arrogant with his airs of cleanliness and scorn for the dirt and smell of the Dalit street, but is drawn in as a leader of an active youth association i.e. Khazari Arts Troupe; Anthony, full of tricks but concerned for justice; and many others. But individuals are unimportant in this novel; neither Jayaraju nor Anthony is mentioned much in the latter half of the book, and references are mainly to the youth as a group, both among Parayars and Pallars. The idyllic bonding between the two communities built through cultural events, sports and celebration of festivals turns out to be a mere façade to mask the burning Jealousies over socio-economic issues. The bloody caste clashes begin with a Hindu Pallar murdering a Christian Parayar. That also for the sake of upper

caste people, Naickars. The rest of the novel deals with a series of retaliations and counter retaliations ending in a bloody caste clash”. (38)

Azhagarasan's introduction rightfully points out to the reader that Bama's perception of the novel is subjugated with yet reasonable Parayar, and the cruel, insensitive Pallar is very clear. The result of these clashes is that young Dalit men are forced to live in hiding, children restricted to go to school, women widowed and children orphaned. The loss on both the sides finally teaches them to realize their folly and also understand the role of dominant castes and state machinery especially the police in perpetrating their animosity. The story ends with yet another killing of an innocent Parayar by the furious Pallars leading to a serious re-think in both the caste groups. The divide and rule policy has been followed and the strategy is identified finally. The Pallars and Parayars confess and decide to sink their differences and reveal their unity at their panchayat poles.

Bama has seen in the way human relationships are broken and caste aside ;the indifference and lack of concern; killing people with words or with silence; mocking those from weaker section of society; denying basic humanity to those caught in the trap of poverty. (sivanagaiah.blogspot.com/2009_10_01_archive.html).

Pawar narrates an episode in the text when she goes to deliver the baskets woven by her mother to her customer's house where she would not be allowed to enter in but instead stand outside their houses on the threshold. Pawar would put the baskets down and the customers would “sprinkle water on them to wash away the pollution and only then they would touch them”. (Pawar, 65) and would “drop coins in his hands from above, avoiding contact as if their hands would have burnt had they touched his’.” (ibid,65).

There is one more narration when Pawar would move to Ratnagiri with her husband. The landlady informed them to look for another accommodation due to the identification of their caste.” My earlier landlady was a maidservant and this landlady was a municipal councillor. Yet the maid and the honourable councillor were united on one point: caste (206). The atrocities against Dalits is still being continued.

In *Vanmam*, the powerful presence of gender seems to be missing unlike in Bama's Karukku and Sangati. The women are in fringes. The worse factor is that they are not sure what

they say or do. There is a portrayal of women abusing themselves on each other by the respective communities. She goes on to elaborate that Dalit woman is not even considered as a 'subject' and caste was never considered to be a subject for discussion in feminist circles. Anyhow efforts have been seriously made among feminist thinkers and activists to reconstruct the history of Dalit feminism in India.

Sharmila Rege's *Writing Caste, Writing Gender* and “*We also Made History: Women in Ambedkerite Movement*” by Urmila Pawar and Meenakshi Moon (Tr: Wandana Sonalkar) are recent additions in that effort. It is unfortunate to note that Dalit feminism has been polarised and criticised and in the process. To conclude, Pallars and Parayars became Dalits. It shows the unity of both the castes to conquer the caste hierarchy which is made possible only with education. It is education that gave them empowerment. Empowerment is development in terms of social realisation which Dr. B.R. Ambedkar’s life mission shows us as a right remedy. His philosophy can provide right therapy to social disease. The mechanics of social order can be built strongly and effectively. This surpasses caste and intercaste differences and allows people to make a move towards social reality of egalitarianism.

Bama's texts have never worked on the victimhood of Dalits. The agency of Dalits has been powerfully presented in all her writings. Though *Vanmam* has entered a highly problematic area, we owe it to her for having dared to open up an embarrassing debate in however preliminary a form.

“.....Dalit literature is deeply immersed in life’s struggle. The Dalit world is filled with dreadful, terrible, humiliating events. Dalit writers cannot escape being tied physically and mentally to this world. Dalit writers are doing the difficult work of portraying this life, through personal experience and empathy, absorbing it from all sides in their sensibility. To live this life is painful enough; it can be equally painful to recreate it on the mental level. Dalit writers are deeply involved in this process.”
(Jadhav, 1992: 303)

The key to both the narratives is the creation of a literary space. Here is the place where the autobiographies are produced of Dalit voices and recovery and mobilization of Dalit women’s works are made. Defining this space, Rege in her essay says, “A Dalit Feminist Standpoint” would be to understand the politics of knowledge generation when marginalised

voices begin to gain public voices. This in turn provides a critique of the failure of the dominant group to interrogate their privileged position since the subject of its knowledge is embodied and visible. (Rege, 2003: 98).

To conclude, Bama opines that marginalized people have been pushed to the very edges of the society have to put aside their internal enmities if they are to reclaim their self respect and their rightful place in society. Here Bama raises a question. She asks the society “how can one live in peace knowing that violence may erupt anytime?” and she answers “every human being should be seen as a human being and respected as a human being that is the goal of the Dalits in the novel Vanamam. And they need a society in which every person is equal” she concludes “Will it ever be reality?”

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